

DECISION MAKING UNDER
UNCERTAINTY IN A FAMILY-OWNED
BUSINESS: A CASE OF COMMODITY
SUDDEN PRICE DECLINE

ABSTRACT

This case study highlights the strategic challenges faced by Mehmood and Brothers, a family-owned wholesale firm operating in the rice market of Sukkur Pakistan. Over several decades the firm built a strong and stable position by relying on experience-based decision making, and close customer relationships with rice as its main source of revenue. In early 2023 a sudden increase in market supply caused rice prices to drop sharply, putting the firm under significant operational pressure. To respond, Mehmood, the owner, thought to stop rice sales to protect the value of their inventory expecting the market would recover. However, he also had the concerns that decline in prices might continue, and the interruption in supply to customers lead to a slowdown in overall business activity. The case shows the difficulties of making managerial decisions under uncertainty and highlights the balance between protecting short-term finances and maintaining long-term customer relationships. It is designed to encourage discussion in business and economics courses in the context of commodity markets.

DECISION MAKING UNDER UNCERTAINTY IN A FAMILY-OWNED BUSINESS: A CASE OF COMMODITY SUDDEN PRICE DECLINE

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INTRODUCTION

Mehmood and Brothers, a family-owned business, started its business operations as a retailer of staple food items – sugar, pulses, grams, oil, floor, rice etc. at small level, in Khairpur¹ Sindh in 1975. The business focused on quality and convenient service to build customer relationships, and as the customer base grew, the sales volume increased. This paved the way for the retailer to expand its business operations by increasing product variety, purchasing bulk quantities from suppliers at better prices, and improving inventory management. With a greater number of customers and higher sales, the firm gradually captured a larger share of the local market. Although the business was initially established in Khairpur, the family's standing residence and strong social and commercial connections in Sukkur provided foundation for relocating the business operations from Khairpur to Sukkur. In 1980, the family relocated its business to Sukkur². With this strategic shift, the firm expanded itself from a small retailer to a big wholesaler. Currently, the firm operates as a wholesaler offering variety of products including pulses, grams, jaggery, and floor with primary focus on rice. Additionally, the firm serves a diversified customer base including both business-to-consumer (B2C) and business-to-business (B2B) segments. Under the B2C segment, the firm deals with individual and household consumers who purchase staple food items in small quantities for personal consumption. In the B2B segment, the firm supplies products in bulk to small retailers, local shopkeepers, and other wholesalers who rely on the firm for consistent quality, competitive pricing, and timely availability. On the supply side, the firm purchases its products from different rice mills through brokers and from regional *mandis*³ according to customer demand. Buying from different sources allows the firm to compare prices and quality before purchasing. This approach helps the firm control costs, maintain product quality, and ensure availability of products, enabling it to offer competitive prices to its customers. With nearly five decades of experience, the firm stands as a renowned wholesaler in *Golimar*, the commercial region of Sukkur. This case study highlights the firm's operational journey, explores the challenges it currently faces, and evaluates the opportunities for improving efficiency and sustaining long-term growth in a competitive marketplace.

Variety of Products

As a wholesaler, the firm offers a wide range of staple food products, including pulses, jaggery, and various types of grams, and flour, all of which are used in daily household consumption. Despite this diversified product portfolio, rice remains the firm's core product. Since rice is a primary staple, other food items are commonly purchased alongside it, allowing the firm to apply a cross-selling strategy effectively. By supplying rice in large quantities, the firm increases the sales of complementary products

¹ **Khairpur:** A district in northern Sindh province of Pakistan, known for its agricultural economy.

² **Sukkur:** A district in northern Sindh province of Pakistan, known for its agricultural economy.

³ **Mandi:** In South Asian languages such as Urdu, Punjabi, and Hindi, the word *mandi* historically refers to a commercial hub where traders gather to buy and sell goods, especially agricultural commodities.

such as pulses, jaggery, and flour. The business deals in multiple varieties of rice, including Banaspati, Sella, and Totta Chawal⁴, which enables it to serve different customer preferences and price segments. With this combination of product variety and effective cross-selling, the firm not only increases overall sales volume but also enhances customer retention, improves revenue stability, and strengthens its position as a trusted one-stop wholesale supplier in the market.

Exhibit 1: Product Portfolio

Category	Products Include
Rice	Banaspati, Sella, Totta Chawal
Pulses (Daal)	Daal Chana, Daal Moong, Daal Mash, Masoor Daal
Jaggery (Gur)	Solid Jaggery, Powdered Jaggery
Grams (Chana)	Whole Chickpeas
Flour	Wheat Floor, Gram Floor

Exhibit 2: Supply and Distribution chain

⁴Totta Chawal: Head broken rice.

Rice Industry

Rice is one of the Pakistan's major crops, a staple food⁵, and a key export commodity. Being a staple food, it is one of the significant crops for Pakistani households. Consistently ranking among top three exporting commodities, its range is 10%–13% (ProPakistani.pk) of total exports depending on global demand and pricing. Along with India and Thailand, Pakistan stands among one of the top rice exporters in the world accounting for approximately 7% to 11% of world rice exports. Rice cultivation in Pakistan is dominated by Punjab, with Sindh standing at second highest contributor, and both provinces showing overall growth in area and production. Main varieties include Basmati (premium, aromatic) and IRRI (non-aromatic, mass consumption). Its supply goes through several stages. First, farmers sell paddy to the traders or mills where it undergoes through processing, where rice mills clean, polish, and grade the rice. After processing, it is either exported or sold to wholesalers, then to retailers, and finally it flows to the consumers.

Prices are influenced by domestic factors such as crop yield, water availability, input costs; government policies like minimum support price (MSP), subsidies; and international factors; for instance, export demand, global prices, and currency exchange rates. Though rice industry in Pakistan exports a huge amount in the global market, it also faces some challenges, like climate change and water scarcity, rising production costs, and storage and transportation inefficiencies. Rice is significant cash crop, contributing 5.7% of total value added in agriculture sector and 1.3% to GDP and serving as an important source of earning foreign reserves. Additionally, it supports rural livelihood and employment, generating several job opportunities throughout its cultivation, processing, and export.

Market - In the Sukkur Region

In Sukkur, rice cultivation is the most prominent agricultural activity, with IRRI-6 variety being the most dominant (65%), B-2000, and Shandar⁶ also being produced. The primary cultivation practice of the farmers is in the Kharif season.⁷ The marketing chain commences at the farm level, where farmers harvest and prepare paddy for sale, accruing sizeable costs on land rent, inputs, and labor. The production costs on average per acreage are shared with Rs. 44,310, which covers the expenses of land preparation, seed, fertilizers, harvesting, and marketing. Usually, farmers sell their harvest to local markets through commission agents and during the process, they pay around 8% commission along with additional costs for loading, unloading, and transportation (Rs. 6,600 per acre). Gross returns per acre on an average basis amount to Rs. 80,200 which in turn gives rise to net income of Rs. 35,890 and an input-output ratio of 1:1.80 suggesting moderate profitability. Despite this, the farmers must cope with the problems caused by high input costs, reliance on middlemen for credit and sales, and low mechanization. Thus, the rice market in Sukkur has the characteristics of a traditional system of

⁵ **Staple Food:** These are basic essential food commodity used in everyday cooking, such as pulses, grains, and flour.

⁶ **Shandar:** refers to a **local variety of rice** grown in the Sukkur region.

⁷ **Kharif season:** Cropping season in India during the monsoon, sown in June–July and harvested in September–October.

farmers, agents, and traders with profitability determined by the factors of production and marketing costs.

Mehmood Ghani – journey in the business

Mehmood, the eldest son of the family, was born in Sukkur. He had his intermediate (his highest education) from Govt Degree College Sukkur., He used to come to his father to help him in business. Most of his time he would spend with his father on the shop. Slowly and gradually, he started learning the norms of business: how it operates, how to deal with customers, employees and other individuals who interact in the business. He was just twenty when he, for the first time, purchased the stock of commodities for business. He started taking active parts in business transactions. Being the eldest son, he had more responsibilities of the firm than his other brothers (two in number). He knew in future he has to take on the business; he accepted the job wholeheartedly. In fact, it was his passion to be engaged in the business as he grew up with it. He would know much more about the business than many others in the market.

After the death of his father in 2015, it was he who handled the business.

He used to overview all the business-related activities by himself, dealing with suppliers, customers, employees etc. He had great knowledge of business which he started applying practically. Having a risk-taking personality, he used to take risks according to what situation demanded from him. Being a foresighted person, he led the firm to new heights of success in the market. He led the business from front. The net income of its income statements was increasing period after period. He had strong prudence of the situations- the rates (prices), behavior of customers and suppliers, how to manage stocks etc. Everything was fine apart from that.

The Situation

It was a cold winter evening in the late February of 2023, Mehmood was in his deep thoughts with his face as pale as death. Ahmed, his eldest son, appeared in the *Godam*⁸. “Salam Baba, May I have a seat?” said Ahmed. Mehmood replied with a positive response. “Baba, why are you stressing on it that much? It is the part of business and happens with everyone. Everything will be fine. Have faith in Allah.” Ahmed tried hard that in some way or the other his father didn’t stress on something that grabbed the smile from his father. “How couldn’t I analyze the market and predicted accordingly? See, how bad does my decision affect the business?” He said to his son but more to himself.

It all began on 11 January 2023, during a period when the firm was still operating in a stable and predictable manner. From December 2022 through January 2023, they consistently procured around 18,000 to 20,000 bags of 25 kg rice, sourced directly from mills as well as through commission agents. Rice was their major product, functioning as the foundation of their business model. Its steady sales allowed them to cross-sell pulses, jaggery, and other agricultural products, making rice central to maintain both revenue and customer flow. Throughout January 2023, operations

⁸ *Godam*: is a warehouse or storage place where agricultural produce like grains is stored safely before sale or distribution

remained normal, with no immediate signs of market disturbance. However, shortly after 11 January, they observed that the overall supply of rice entering the market was beginning to rise more than usual. Even though this increase was noticeable, it did not cause an instant drop in price. The firm assumed that the market would self-regulate as it often had during past fluctuations and continued their normal trading activities. The situation shifted significantly in February 2023, when the accumulated high supply finally began impacting prices. Starting from the first week of February, rice prices started to decline steadily.

Concerned by the event, Mehmood had different ways to deal with the situation; however, this time he was more cautious to apply any because little more mishap, and the game is over. Of the ideas, one was to stop the sales for a few days to escape the losses, but his foresightedness warned for more concerns. The idea was based on the expectation that the market, through its natural adjustment mechanisms—such as demand catching up with supply or traders reducing excess stock— would bring prices back to normal levels. However, the opposite was also possible to occur. Instead of stabilizing, the market might have continued to move downward, and rice prices kept falling. While the firm held their stock, waiting for the expected rebound, their customers—who depended on consistent supplies— would have begun seeking other wholesalers to meet their own distribution needs. This brief disruption could allow competing suppliers to fill the gap.

The decline in the price of rice did not affect the rice alone, rather it also had alarming effects on cross selling concept. The situation led to dramatic financial loss, which would be the decider of the future of business. All the way, Mehmood had to deal with the problem, were backed by lots of concerns and he was in a position he could not afford any mishap. What next?

Mehmood & Brothers

Financial Statements

Prepared for case study teaching and discussion

Income Statement

For the three months ended March 31, 2023

Particulars	Amount (Rs.)
Cash Sales Revenue	22,50,000
Cost of Goods Sold	30,00,000
Gross Loss	(7,50,000)
Operating Expenses	3,50,000
Net Loss	(11,00,000)

Statement of Financial Position

As at March 31, 2023

Assets	Amount (Rs.)
Inventory (Net)	1,40,00,000
Cash on Hand	70,00,000
Account Receivables	20,00,000
Other Current Assets	30,00,000
Total Assets	2,60,00,000

Equity & Liabilities	Amount (Rs.)
Owner's Equity (after loss)	1,35,00,000
Trade Payables	1,25,00,000
Total Equity & Liabilities	2,60,00,000

Key Financial Ratios (Before vs After Shock)

Ratio	Before Shock	After Shock
Gross Margin	8%	-33%
Net Profit Margin	4%	-49%
Inventory Turnover	6.2x	1.8x

Notes:

1. Sales for Jan–Mar 2023 are low to reflect seasonal slump and market disruption.

2. inventory was purchased at higher prices earlier; the decline in market prices led to losses and lower margins.
3. These statements are illustrative, prepared solely for academic case-study analysis.

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Teaching Notes Section

1. Case Synopsis

Mehmood and Brothers is a family-owned wholesale business operating in Sukkur, Sindh, with a business history extending over nearly five decades. Established initially as a small retail outlet dealing in staple food items, the firm gradually expanded into a major wholesaler, serving both business-to-consumer and business-to-business markets. Over time, rice emerged as the firm's core product, acting not only as the primary revenue generator but also as a key driver of cross-selling for complementary items such as pulses, jaggery, and flour.

Following the death of the founder in 2015, the business came under the leadership of Mehmood Ghani, whose extensive practical experience and market understanding contributed to consistent growth. In early 2023, the firm faced an unexpected market disruption when an increase in rice supply led to a sustained decline in prices. Anticipating a natural market correction, Mehmood thought to halt rice sales for sometime to avoid immediate inventory losses. There were concerns that prices might continue to fall, and during this brief interruption, several regular customers might shift to competing wholesalers. The event led to unprecedented financial loss to the firm. The case highlights the strategic challenges of decision-making under uncertainty in commodity-based markets.

2. Learning Objectives

After engaging with this case, participants should be able to:

- Analyze managerial decision-making under conditions of market uncertainty and price disruptions.
- Evaluate inventory-related risks in commodity-based wholesale businesses.
- Examine the relationship between pricing decisions and customer retention.
- Apply economic and strategic frameworks to assess real-world business challenges.
- Develop alternative managerial responses to supply-driven market disruptions.

3. Target Audience and Prerequisites

Target Audience

This case is intended for students, researchers, and business professionals seeking to understand economic uncertainty and the role of data-driven decision-making in managerial practice. It illustrates how market volatility and supply-driven price fluctuations impact inventory, pricing, and customer behavior, and emphasizes the importance of leveraging data and market insights to inform strategic decisions in family-owned, commodity-focused businesses.

Prerequisites

Participants are expected to possess a basic understanding of demand and supply dynamics, inventory management principles, and competitive market behavior.

4. Key Issues and Analytical Frameworks

Key Issues:

- Reliance on experience-based intuition rather than structured market analysis
- Inventory risk arising from holding large stock volumes during declining price trends
- Customer defection caused by temporary interruption in supply
- Heavy dependence on rice as the firm's anchor product
- Absence of formal contingency planning for adverse market conditions.
- Suggested Analytical Frameworks
- Demand and supply analysis
- Inventory and working capital management
- Customer Relationship Management (CRM)
- SWOT analysis
- Decision-making under uncertainty.

5. Discussion Questions

1. Why did rice occupy a central role in the business model of Mehmood and Brothers?
2. What market signals suggested that rice prices were likely to decline in early 2023?
3. How would you evaluate the idea of halting the rice sales temporarily from a strategic perspective?
4. In what ways could the interruption in sales affect customer relationships and competitive positioning?
5. What alternative strategies could the firm have adopted to manage declining prices while retaining customers?
6. How did the decline in rice sales influence the firm's cross-selling of other products?
7. What broader lessons does the case offer regarding intuition-based decision-making in family-owned businesses?

6. Teaching Plan and Time Allocation (90 Minutes)

Introduction and Case Context (10 minutes)

The session may begin with a brief overview of the firm's background, industry setting, and the central managerial dilemma. Emphasis may be placed on the importance of rice within the firm's overall business model and the market conditions that led to the price decline.

Small Group Discussion (30 minutes)

Participants may be divided into small groups to analyze the idea of stopping rice sales. Each group may be asked to identify the risks involved, assess the potential impact on customers and competitors, and propose alternative strategies that could have been adopted.

Plenary Discussion and Debrief (40 minutes)

Groups may present their analyses, followed by a moderated discussion connecting participant insights to broader concepts such as demand–supply dynamics, inventory risk, and customer retention. The discussion may explore both short-term financial considerations and long-term strategic consequences.

Conclusion and Key Reflections (10 minutes)

The session may conclude with a synthesis of key insights and lessons drawn from the

discussion, highlighting the importance of balancing financial prudence with relationship management in commodity-based markets.